

Multi-Group Cross Section Generation with Peacock for Fast Reactor Applications

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ABSTRACT

This work introduces an innovative two-step neutronics methodology for fast reactor analysis. It couples the new Studsvik Scandpower three-dimensional Monte Carlo code Peacock with the nodal diffusion solver SIMULATE5. Peacock can generate multi-group cross sections via continuous-energy simulations, employing spatial and energy condensation suitable for fast reactor spectra. These cross sections are then passed to SIMULATE5 for efficient core calculations. The approach is validated using a 2D model of the MET-1000 sodium-cooled fast reactor, demonstrating excellent agreement with reference standalone Monte Carlo results in terms of eigenvalue and power distribution, while significantly reducing computational costs. This highlights the potential of this methodology for accurate and scalable fast reactor core design.

Keywords: Peacock, SIMULATE5, multi-group, cross section, fast reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

Historically, light-water reactor (LWR) neutronics analysis has employed a two-step calculation process, where assembly-homogenized cross sections (XS) are generated from detailed two-dimensional transport simulations and passed to a three-dimensional nodal diffusion solver for full reactor calculations. Coupled with a series of innovations developed specifically for LWR analysis, such as assembly discontinuity factors [1] this methodology became the *de facto* means for LWR analysis and has enjoyed great success.

Neutronics analysis of fast reactors offers unique aspects from that for LWRs. The relative smoothness of the radial flux profile, large core leakage contributions in both the radial and axial directions, and the effective lack of a thermal component of the neutron spectrum creates substantial challenges for conventional two-step calculation methodologies. These characteristics demand alternative modeling strategies to accurately capture the physics of fast reactor systems.

This study develops and verifies a two-step neutronics methodology that integrates the new Studsvik Scandpower (SSP) three-dimensional Monte Carlo (MC) code Peacock [2] with the nodal diffusion solver SIMULATE5 [3]. Where earlier SSP transport methods depended on pre-processed multi-group (MG) nuclear data, Peacock performs direct continuous-energy evaluations, enabling direct assessment of new nuclear data and its effects on reactor performance. Developed under SSP's Nuclear Quality Assurance-1 (NQA-1) program, Peacock implements 10 CFR Part 21 error reporting, providing

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traceability and enabling engineers to move efficiently from data investigation to deployment in downstream reactor design analyses.

Peacock is currently developed to generate high-fidelity MG XS for advanced reactors by performing continuous-energy MC simulations with enhanced tallying and energy-condensation methods. These XSs are passed to SIMULATE5 for efficient full-core nodal diffusion analysis. The methodology is demonstrated on a 2D benchmark of the MET-1000 [4], a sodium-cooled fast reactor (SFR) concept. The workflow comprises: (1) detailed geometry and material specification in Peacock, (2) energy-group condensation and spatial homogenization to produce SIMULATE5-compatible XSs, and (3) nodal diffusion calculations in SIMULATE5 that are validated against reference MC results to quantify accuracy. While SIMULATE5 has proven highly effective for performing full-core nodal diffusion analysis with these XSs, it is important to emphasize that Peacock output is not limited to any specific diffusion solver. The MG XS generated by Peacock are compatible with a wide range of multi-group neutron diffusion methods, making it a versatile tool for reactor physics analysis.

2. MULTI-GROUP CROSS SECTIONS GENERATION

To perform accurate nodal diffusion calculations, the solver requires a set of homogenized multi-group cross sections that characterize neutron behavior within each spatial node. These typically include a total XS, absorption XS, fission XS, nu-fission XS, kappa-fission XS, scattering matrices, fission spectrum and diffusion coefficients. Among these, the diffusion coefficient is particularly crucial, as it governs neutron leakage and spatial coupling between nodes. In practice, the diffusion coefficient is often derived from the transport cross section, which accounts for anisotropic scattering effects and provides a more physically accurate representation of neutron migration than the total XS alone.

MG XSs are condensed using the flux-weighted average [5], [6]

$$\Sigma_{x,g} = \frac{\int_V dV \int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} dE \Sigma_x(r, E) \phi(r, E)}{\int_V dV \int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} dE \phi(r, E)} = \frac{R_{x,g}}{\phi_g}, \quad (1)$$

where $\phi(r, E)$ is the space-energy-dependent flux, V is the volume, g is the group index with upper and lower energy boundaries of E_g and E_{g-1} , $\Sigma_x(r, E)$ is a space-energy-dependent XS, and the XS type x is t (total), f (fission), a (absorption), nsf (nu-fission), or ksf (kappa-fission). The $P0$ and $P1$ scattering matrices are similarly spatially homogenized. Theoretically, the l^{th} flux moment should be used to condense the corresponding l^{th} order scattering matrices:

$$\Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow g'}^l = \frac{\frac{1}{V} \int_V dV \int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} dE \int_{E_{g'}}^{E_{g'-1}} dE' \int_{-1}^1 d\mu \Sigma_s^l(r, E \rightarrow E', \mu) \phi^l(r, E)}{\phi_g^l}. \quad (2)$$

However, direct Monte Carlo estimation of flux moments is subject to high statistical uncertainty due to the inherently noisy nature of directional MC tallies. To address this, the flux moment is approximated as proportional to the scalar flux [7]:

$$\phi^l(r, E) = C_l \phi^0(r, E), \quad (3)$$

where C_l is a proportionality constant. Eq. (3) enables practical scoring of the $P \not\approx$ scattering matrix using scalar flux and Legendre polynomials as:

$$\Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow g'}^l = \frac{\frac{1}{V} \int_V dV \int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} dE \int_{E_{g'}}^{E_{g'-1}} dE' \int_{-1}^1 d\mu \Sigma_s^l(r, E \rightarrow E', \mu) P_l(\mu) \phi(r, E)}{\phi_g}, \quad (4)$$

where μ denotes the cosine scattering angle, $P_l(\mu)$ denotes the Legendre polynomial, and l denotes the order of the Legendre polynomial.

The probability distribution over the outgoing fission energy is defined as the fission spectrum χ_g :

$$\chi_g = \frac{\int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} dE \int_0^\infty dE' v \Sigma_f(r, E' \rightarrow E) \phi(r, E)}{\int_0^\infty dE \int_0^\infty dE' v \Sigma_f(r, E' \rightarrow E) \phi(r, E)}. \quad (5)$$

For transport XS approximation, the outflow correction method [8] as in Eq. (6) is commonly applied, as inflow correction is impractical due to the limitations in MC tallies of flux moments.

$$\Sigma_{tr,g} = \Sigma_{t,g} - \sum_{g'} \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow g'}^1, \quad (6)$$

The diffusion coefficient (D) is then calculated as in Eq. (7).

$$D_g = \frac{1}{3\Sigma_{tr,g}} \quad (7)$$

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This work verifies the two-step code system Peacock/SIMULATE5 (PS5) against the reference MC Peacock for a 2D slice of the 1000 MWth metallic sodium-cooled fast reactor MET-1000 as shown in

Figure 1. The core contains 180 fuel, 114 radial reflector, 66 radial shield, and 19 control sub-assemblies (SAs). Fuel SAs are grouped into inner and outer zones with 78 and 102 assemblies, respectively, featuring variable plutonium content. Reactivity is controlled by two systems: 15 primary and 4 secondary control SAs. Each fuel SA houses 271 HT-9-clad fuel pins on a triangular pitch inside a hexagonal HT-9 duct. Additional model details are provided in the benchmark report [4].

Figure 1. MET-1000 radial configuration.

A standardized framework is established for generating MG XS for all fast reactor components. The study uses a 24-group structure based on ECCO-33 [8], with the last ten thermal groups merged into a single thermal group. This energy group structure is designed to reduce high statistical uncertainty in MC flux tallies in the thermal range due to the fast energy spectrum of this problem and thereby improve the reliability of the condensed data.

Fuel SA XSs are produced using a single 2D fuel SA model with reflective boundary conditions (BCs), shown in Figure 2(a). For non-multiplying regions, homogenized XSs are generated from 2D supercell models Figure 2(b), in which the target region is centered and surrounded by fuel SAs to reproduce representative spectral and spatial flux conditions. To capture the spectral shift at the fuel-reflector interface, a dedicated 2D radial reflector model (RRM) is used [5, 8]; the RRM applies a vacuum BC on the outer radial side, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. (a) 2D fuel SA model and (b) 2D supercell model.

Figure 3. 2D radial reflector model.

The Peacock XS calculations produced 24-group macroscopic XS and formatted them for compatibility with the nodal diffusion code SIMULATE5. As this calculation is for a single state-point, no XS functionalization or case matrix was necessary. These multi-group data enabled full-core 2D analysis of the multiplication factor (k_{eff}) and radial power distribution under all-rods-out (ARO) conditions. It is noted that the intra assembly normalization in SIMULATE5 is set to six triangles per hexagon. A high-fidelity, full-core Peacock calculation is used as the reference solution. All simulations used a nuclear data library based on ENDF/B-VII.1; fuel and structural material temperatures are fixed at 900 K and 600 K, respectively.

For the reference MC solution, the criticality calculation uses 50 inactive cycles, 400 active cycles, and 200,000 particle histories per cycle on 64 processors, with an estimated runtime of 191.8 hours (wall-clock time). For MG XS generation a reduced setup—50 inactive cycles, 400 active cycles, and 50,000 histories per cycle—is used. Cross section generation for all nodal components (inner and outer fuel SA, empty duct, reflector SA, and shielding SA) requires roughly 5 hours in total. The SIMULATE5 nodal diffusion solves the calculation completes within seconds using OpenMP with 4 threads, illustrating the computational efficiency of the two-step workflow.

Table I summarizes the k_{eff} results from MET-1000 2D whole-core calculations at beginning-of-cycle ARO conditions, comparing Peacock with two PS5 cases using reflector XSs generated from (1) a supercell model and (2) a RRM.

Table I. MET-1000 core k_{eff} , PS5 vs. Peacock.

Code	k_{eff}	Diff. (pcm)
Peacock	1.21979(5)	--
PS5 (1)	1.22362	383
PS5 (2)	1.22179	200

Figure 4 and Figure 5 present the radial power distribution of MET-1000 at ARO from Peacock and PS5; Peacock results exhibit relative standard deviations below 0.12%. Because MC method is inherently stochastic, residual asymmetries may persist despite large history counts. To mitigate statistical asymmetry, Peacock outputs were averaged across rotational symmetry sectors to provide a consistent, symmetry-aligned reference for PS5. Figure 6 shows the absolute percentage difference between Peacock and PS5, and Table II lists the maximum and root-mean-square (RMS) differences. These statistics quantify PS5's deviation from the Peacock reference and thereby evaluate the accuracy of the nodal diffusion solution.

Figure 4. Peacock radial power distribution (sixth-core symmetry).

Figure 5. PS5 radial power distribution (sixth-core symmetry).

The results show close agreement between the Peacock reference and nodal diffusion solutions using Peacock-generated multi-group cross sections. When reflector XSs are taken from the supercell model, the eigenvalue bias is under 400 pcm, with radial power RMS and maximum differences of 0.77% and 1.50%, respectively. A clear in-out power tilt indicates that PS5 underestimates neutron leakage into reflector assemblies relative to Peacock for the case with reflector XS from supercell calculations. Using reflector XSs from the RRM reduces the eigenvalue bias to roughly 200 pcm and lowers radial power RMS and maximum errors to 0.36% and 0.77% respectively. The improvement is attributed to the RRM better capturing spectral shifts at the fuel-reflector interface. Therefore, RRM-derived reflector XSs are recommended for nodal diffusion core calculations to improve reactivity and peripheral assembly power predictions.

Figure 6. Comparisons in radial power distribution.

Table II. Summary of radial power comparison, PS5 vs. Peacock.

Diff. (%)	RMS	Max.
PS5 (1) vs. Peacock	0.77	1.50
PS5 (2) vs. Peacock	0.36	0.77

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Peacock/SIMULATE5 two-step methodology has been successfully applied to the 2D MET-1000 SFR benchmark, demonstrating both accuracy and efficiency in fast reactor core analysis. Using reflector XSs from the supercell model, the eigenvalue discrepancy was below 400 pcm, with radial power RMS and maximum errors under 0.77% and 1.50%, respectively. When using RRM-based XSs, the eigenvalue difference improved to approximately 200 pcm, and radial power RMS and maximum errors were reduced to 0.36% and 0.77%, respectively. These results confirm that RRM-generated XSs more effectively capture spectral shifts at the fuel-reflector interface, leading to improved agreement in reactivity and peripheral power distribution. The Peacock/SIMULATE5 framework is therefore a promising tool for fast reactor design and benchmarking. While SIMULATE5 has demonstrated strong performance in full-core nodal diffusion analysis using Peacock-generated XSs, it is important to emphasize that Peacock is not tied to any specific diffusion solver. The MG XSs produced by Peacock are broadly compatible with a variety of neutron diffusion methods, making it a flexible and extensible tool for advanced reactor physics analysis.

To further enhance the accuracy and applicability of the two-step framework, future efforts will focus on extending the methodology to full 3D core simulations. This will enable the evaluation of axial effects, such as control rod insertion, axial leakage, and power peaking, which are not captured in 2D models. Additionally, the implementation of super-homogenization or other equivalence factors could be investigated to improve the consistency between heterogeneous MC reference solutions and homogenized nodal diffusion calculations. Incorporating super-homogenization factors would be expected to reduce local power discrepancies, particularly in regions with strong absorption when inserting control rods. These developments will support more accurate and robust fast reactor design and safety analysis.

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